

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4 (2)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqov vich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayev vich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayev vich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyev vich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyev vich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyev vich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixojaga o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyev vich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdulkarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA “AKT XIZMATLARI” TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI.....	14
Shermatov Sherzod Xotamovich RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	20
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich, Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich TIJORAT BANKLARINING BYUDJET MABLAG’LARI HISOBIGA MOLİYALASHTIRILADIGAN LOYIHALARDAGI ISHTIROKINI KUCHAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	26
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o’g’li KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO’NALISHLARI.....	33
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O’TISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI VA UNI O’ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO’LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	38
Ne’matova Mavsuma, Xolmamatov Diyorbek ВЛИЯНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ НА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	43
Буранова Лола Вахобовна ФИНТЕХ-ЭКОСИСТЕМА КАК ФАКТОР ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО И УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	54
Эшмуротов Дониёр Ихтиёр угли ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	60
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Matyoqub qizi, Fayzullayeva Zamira Alijonovna XIZMAT KO’RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	64
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG’OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o’g’li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	73
Abdullo Sohobov O’ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARI JADALLASHUVI VA UNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	84
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich KORXONALAR MOLİYAVIY HOLATINI MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI (MHXS) ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	91
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o’g’li BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	95
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi O’ZBEKISTON VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA BENEFITSIAR MULKDOR KONSEPSIYASINI QO’LLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	100
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich O’ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O’TISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH (GDP, BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYALAR KESIMIDA).....	106
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	

INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	111
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi IPOTEKA BOZORI MUAMMOLARINING EMPERIK TAHLILI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	118
Olokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi MILLIY IQTISODIYOT RAQOBATIDA NAZARIY VA AMALIY QARASHLAR.....	122
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna KORPORATIV BANK XIZMATLARIGA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA ZAMONAVIY BIZNES MODELLARNI JORIY ETISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	128
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INDONESIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY.....	133
Ibrokhimova Iroda Ikromjon Kizi. Askolani. Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA REKRUTING AGENTLIKLARINING O'RNI.....	142
Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	148
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна BUDJET DAROMADLARI TARKIBIDAGI SOLIQLARNING ULUSHINI BOSHQARISH.....	156
Abduraxmonova Gulmira Sobir qizi RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AVTOSERVIS SHOHOVCHALARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	161
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND ITS RECOGNITION IN ACCOUNTING AS AN OBJECT OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS.....	165
Zafar Qodirov Abdivaxobovich O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	170
Ibragimov G'ayrat Ablaqulovich. Tursunov Ozod Matlubovich Shukurova Nilufar Qahramonova IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	175
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA INTEGRAL KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	179
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.....	184
Wang Biao USTAMA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH XARAJATLARINING MAZMUNI VA UNI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MUVOFIQ TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	190
Tashnazarova Dilfuza Samiddinovna INTEGRATSIYA SAMARADORLIGINI O'LCHASHNING METODOLOGIK MODELI VA INDIKATORLAR TIZIMI.....	195
Aliqulov Abbas Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	202
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	

MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	207
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI	213
L.S. Azimova	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING	218
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin o'g'li	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIKNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	223
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISH ORQALI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMLARI	227
Ergasheva Zarifa Baxtiyarovna	
CHO'L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAJMUASI RIVOJLANTIRISH	232
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
KREDITORLAR REYTINGINI MASHINAVIY O'QITISHGA ASOSLANGAN BASHORATLASH ALGORITMLARI	237
Beknazarov Ulug'bek Zafar o'g'li	
MIKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORI VA TALAB SHAKLLANISHI OMILLARI	242
Raximov Azizbek Saliyevich	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY Tajribasi: AQSH MISOLIDA.....	246
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARNI JORIY ETISH USULLARI	250
Ashurova Shaxnoza Almasovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	257
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	262
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA MIJOZ QONIQLASHINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA	278
Aqsungul Usenova Tenel qizi, Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti	
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzaboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	283
Azlarova Munira Muhammad-Amin qizi	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI SHAKLLANTIRISH, RIVOJLANTIRISH VA KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH.....	289
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	
IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	294
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	299
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORI MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	304
Abdusalomov Ozodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	311
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI OSHIRISHDA AKT RIVOJLANISHINING O'RNI.....	315
Sadriddinov Ulug'bek Jaloliddin o'g'li QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.....	322
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o'g'li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHIYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	326
Abdullo Sohibov SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	331
Davronov Sanjar Ziyotovich SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINI QABUL QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	336
Ashrapova Noilaxon Niyazxanovna ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI TAHLILI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	340
Ochilov Baxtiyor Muminjonovich THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING.....	346
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin ugli SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	351
Astanakulov Olim Tashtemirovich Muxammad Id Balbaa (Muhammad Eid Balbaa) Habibe Elif Kutlugun (Habibe Elif Kutlugun) GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI FONIDA EKOLOGIK SIYOSAT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	357
Xamzayev Abdushukur Xudoyqulovich INTERNATIONAL MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR UZBEKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, AND ECONOMETRIC EVIDENCE.....	362
Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev Sarvarbek Allayev Erkin ugli Shavkat Asrolovich Ruziev DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	369
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI TAHLILI ("O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJ MISOLIDA).....	373
Barotov Baxtiyor Vaxobovich CHIQUINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	377
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna TRANSPORT LOGISTIKASIDA TAVAKKALCHILIKLARNI SUG'URTALASH: O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSH TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA TAQQOSIY TAHLIL.....	381
Jabborov Islom Xusan o'g'li YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY SALOHIYATINI BARQAROR BOSHQARISH.....	385
Xayrullayev Shaxram Yunus o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SERVIS KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATI BOSHQARUVINING ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI	392
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
BIZNES JARAYONLARI MONITORINGI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	398
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi	
SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOT KONSEPSIYASINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARINI (INDIKATORLARINI) SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	403
Sharifxo'jayeva Xonzodaxon A'lo qizi	
TURIZM QISHLOQLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI TIZIMI	408
Xudaynazarova Dilorom	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUV VA BOSHQARUV HISOB TIZIMINING AMALIYOTI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	416
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
DAVLAT XARIDLARI JARAYONIDA XAVFLARNI IDENTIFIKATSIYA QILISH, TASNIFLASH VA RISKKA ASOSLANGAN ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	421
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
DEVELOPING GARMENT MANUFACTURING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	426
Mahbuba Rahmonova	
Feruz Mansurovna Ollokulova	

DEVELOPING GARMENT MANUFACTURING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Mahbuba Rahmonova
Master's Student in Economics
Termez State University
Email: makhbuba.rakhmonova@gmail.com
Phone: +998 97 810 68 88

Supervisor:
Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova, PhD
Faculty of Economics, Termez State University

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida tikuvchilik xizmatlarini takomillashtirish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot davomida so'rovnoma asosida tikuv xizmatlariga bo'lgan talab va mavjud muammolar, jumladan, xizmat narxining yuqoriligi, bajarish tezligining pastligi hamda individual yondashuv yetishmasligi aniqlangan. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish maqsadida "Tikuvchi.uz" nomli yagona raqamli platforma taklif etilgan. Platforma orqali tikuvchilar va mijozlar o'rtasidagi jarayonlarni optimallashtirish, xizmat sifatini oshirish hamda buyurtmalarni tezkor amalga oshirish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Shuningdek, loyihaning iqtisodiy samaradorligi tahlil qilinib, komissiya, yetkazib berish va reklama xizmatlari orqali barqaror daromad olish imkoniyatlari asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari raqamli platformalarning xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida samarali yechim ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, tikuvchilik xizmati, raqamli platforma, innovatsion texnologiyalar, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, mijozga yo'naltirilganlik, individual yondashuv, elektron xizmatlar, platforma iqtisodiyoti, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, onlayn buyurtma tizimi, yetkazib berish.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются вопросы совершенствования услуг швейного производства в условиях цифровой трансформации. В ходе исследования на основе опроса выявлены спрос на швейные услуги и существующие проблемы, включая высокую стоимость услуг, низкую скорость выполнения заказов и недостаток индивидуального подхода. Для решения данных проблем предложена единая цифровая платформа «Tikuvchi.uz». Платформа позволяет оптимизировать взаимодействие между швеями и клиентами, повысить качество услуг и ускорить выполнение заказов. Также проведён анализ экономической эффективности проекта и обоснованы возможности получения стабильного дохода за счёт комиссий, доставки и рекламных услуг. Результаты исследования показывают, что цифровые платформы являются эффективным решением в сфере услуг.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, швейные услуги, цифровая платформа, инновационные технологии, сфера услуг, клиентоориентированность, индивидуальный подход, электронные услуги, платформенная экономика, экономическая эффективность, система онлайн-заказа, доставка.

Abstract. This article analyzes the improvement of tailoring services in the context of digital transformation. Based on a survey, the study identifies the demand for tailoring services and existing problems, including high service costs, slow order fulfillment, and a lack of individual approach. To address these issues, a unified digital platform called "Tikuvchi.uz" is proposed. The platform enables the optimization of interactions between

tailors and customers, improves service quality, and ensures faster order processing. In addition, the economic efficiency of the project is analyzed, and opportunities for generating stable income through commissions, delivery, and advertising services are substantiated. The research results show that digital platforms are an effective solution in the service sector.

Keywords: digital transformation, tailoring services, digital platform, innovative technologies, service sector, customer orientation, individual approach, electronic services, platform economy, economic efficiency, on-line ordering system, delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, digital transformation plays a significant role in all sectors of the economy, including services and manufacturing. The rapid development of modern technologies, continuous changes in market demand, and increasing competition have reduced the effectiveness of traditional approaches. Therefore, the digitalization of business activities, optimization of operational processes, and strengthening of a customer-oriented approach have become essential tasks for enterprises and service providers.

The tailoring service sector is also influenced by these changes. In this field, it is important to meet individual customer needs and provide high-quality, fast, and reliable services. However, in practice, several problems remain, such as high service costs, delays in order fulfillment, and the inability to fully satisfy customer preferences. These issues highlight the necessity of introducing innovative solutions into the sector.

The use of digital platforms creates opportunities to organize service processes more efficiently, simplify interactions between tailors and customers, and improve overall service quality. In particular, a unified online platform enables more effective order management, payment processing, and service delivery control.

The aim of this article is to analyze ways of improving tailoring services in the context of digital transformation and to justify opportunities for increasing service efficiency through the implementation of the "Tikuvchi.uz" digital platform.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation has become one of the key drivers of economic development and competitiveness in modern economies. According to Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee, the rapid advancement of digital technologies significantly changes traditional business models and increases productivity through automation and data-driven decision-making (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). These transformations create new opportunities for service industries to improve efficiency and customer satisfaction.

In recent years, the concept of the platform economy has gained increasing attention. Digital platforms serve as intermediaries that connect service providers and consumers, reducing transaction costs and improving market transparency. Research shows that platform-based models enhance operational efficiency by simplifying communication, enabling online transactions, and facilitating service delivery processes (Parker et al., 2016). This is particularly important in service sectors where personalization and speed are critical factors.

Customer-oriented approaches are also emphasized in modern literature. Scholars argue that businesses must focus on understanding individual customer needs and delivering customized services to remain competitive. Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller note that customer value and relationship management are essential for sustainable competitiveness (Kotler & Keller, 2016). In tailoring services, personalization plays a crucial role, as customers demand unique designs and precise fitting. However, traditional service models often fail to meet these expectations due to limited communication and inefficient processes.

Furthermore, digitalization contributes to cost reduction and time optimization in service delivery. Studies indicate that integrating digital tools into service systems can significantly decrease operational delays and improve service quality. Michael E. Porter and James Heppelmann emphasize that smart and connected technologies improve operational performance and customer interaction (Porter & Heppelmann, 2014). In addition, online platforms enable real-time interaction between service providers and customers, which enhances trust and satisfaction.

Despite these advantages, several challenges remain in the adoption of digital technologies in small-scale service sectors such as tailoring. Limited technological infrastructure, lack of digital skills, and resistance to change are among the main barriers. Gregory Vial highlights that successful transformation requires both technological readiness and organizational adaptation (Vial, 2019). Therefore, it is essential to develop practical and accessible digital solutions tailored to the specific needs of the industry.

Overall, the existing literature confirms that digital platforms are an effective tool for transforming service industries. They improve efficiency, enhance customer experience, and create new economic opportunities.

These theoretical insights provide a strong foundation for the development of the proposed “Tikuvchi.uz” platform, which aims to address current challenges in tailoring services and improve overall service performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comprehensive research approach to analyze the improvement of tailoring services in the context of digital transformation. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used to ensure the reliability and validity of the research results.

First, a survey method was applied to identify customer demand, preferences, and existing problems in tailoring services. The survey results provided empirical data on key issues such as service costs, delivery time, and the level of individualization in service provision.

Second, analytical and comparative methods were used to evaluate the current state of tailoring services and to identify their main limitations. These methods made it possible to compare traditional service models with digital approaches and to highlight the necessity of transformation.

Based on the collected data, a conceptual model of the “Tikuvchi.uz” digital platform was developed using the modeling method. The platform structure, its functional components, and the stages of service delivery were systematically designed.

In addition, an economic analysis was conducted to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed platform. This included estimating initial investment costs, identifying potential revenue sources, and calculating expected monthly income based on commission fees, delivery services, and advertising opportunities.

Overall, the applied methodology ensured a comprehensive evaluation of both the practical and economic aspects of implementing a digital platform in tailoring services.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The survey results indicate that 51% of respondents use tailoring services, which confirms the existence of stable demand in this sector. However, several key problems were identified. The most significant issue is the high cost of services (37.5%), followed by slow service delivery (36.5%). Additionally, 22.5% of respondents reported that tailors are unable to produce garments according to their preferred style, while 3.5% pointed out low communication quality.

At the same time, the advantages of tailoring services were also highlighted. About 34% of respondents noted the opportunity to choose a preferred style, while 30% emphasized accurate fitting according to body measurements. Furthermore, 16.5% of participants indicated that the ability to select fabric individually increases trust in product quality. These findings demonstrate that personalization is a key value in tailoring services (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Process of Organizing Tailoring Services via a Digital Platform¹

Based on the identified problems, the “Tikuvchi.uz” digital platform was proposed. The platform enables the integration of all service processes, including the registration of tailors, presentation of products, order

¹ Picture 1. Process of Organizing Tailoring Services via a Digital Platform (Developed by the Author).

placement, and payment processing. This system improves transparency, reduces service time, and enhances customer satisfaction.

Economic calculations show that if the platform processes an average of 500 orders per month, with an average order value of 200,000 UZS and a 5% commission rate, the monthly income from commissions would reach 5,000,000 UZS. In addition, delivery services could generate approximately 4,800,000 UZS in revenue, resulting in around 2,000,000 UZS net profit after deducting operational costs. Additional income may also be generated through advertising on the platform.

Overall, the results confirm that the implementation of a digital platform can significantly improve service efficiency, increase customer satisfaction, and ensure stable financial performance.

The findings of this study highlight that digital transformation can significantly improve the efficiency and quality of tailoring services. The identified problems, such as high service costs, slow delivery, and limited personalization, indicate the need for innovative solutions in the sector.

The proposed “Tikuvchi.uz” platform provides a practical solution by integrating all service processes into a single digital system. This approach increases transparency in pricing, reduces service time, and enhances communication between tailors and customers. As a result, customer satisfaction is expected to improve due to faster service and better alignment with individual preferences.

Moreover, the platform creates new opportunities for service providers. It allows tailors to expand their customer base and operate more efficiently. At the same time, students and young specialists can gain practical experience and generate income through participation in the platform. This contributes not only to economic development but also to employment growth.

From an economic perspective, the platform demonstrates strong potential for sustainability. The combination of commission-based income, delivery services, and advertising revenue ensures diversified income sources. This reduces financial risks and supports the long-term viability of the project.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, this study confirms that digital transformation is an effective approach to improving tailoring services. The main challenges identified in the sector can be effectively addressed through the implementation of digital platforms.

The proposed “Tikuvchi.uz” platform enables the optimization of service processes, improves service quality, and increases economic efficiency. It also creates new opportunities for both service providers and customers.

Overall, the implementation of this platform can contribute to the modernization of the service sector and support sustainable economic development. The results of the study demonstrate that digital solutions play a key role in enhancing competitiveness and meeting the evolving needs of consumers.

REFERENCES

1. Erik Brynjolfsson, E., & Andrew McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age: Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies*. New York, NY: W. W. Norton & Company.
2. Geoffrey G. Parker, G., Marshall Van Alstyne, M., & Sangeet Paul Choudary, S. (2016). *Platform revolution*. W. W. Norton & Company.
3. Philip Kotler, P., & Kevin Lane Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing management* (15th ed.). Pearson.
4. Michael E. Porter, M. E., & James E. Heppelmann, J. E. (2014). How smart, connected products are transforming competition. *Harvard Business Review*.
5. Gregory Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118–144.
6. Data prepared based on Google Survey results.
7. Picture 1. Process of organizing tailoring services via a digital platform. Developed by the author.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4 (2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>